

ISSN : 2349-543X

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

TRENDS IN COMMERCE AND ECONOMICS

Indexed by:

Universal
Impact Factor

IMPACT FACTOR
SEARCH

International journal of trends in commerce and economics ISSN: 2349-543X VOL.

14. Issue 1

<http://academicjournalonline.org/index.php/ijtce/issue/archive>

Impact factor 9

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STAGES AND PROSPECTS OF BUDGET ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING REFORM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the process of execution of cost estimates, accountants of budget organizations encountered some accounting issues, which were not clearly explained or instructed in regulatory legal documents. After some accountants of budget organizations perform one or another accounting operation, it becomes known that such accounting operation was performed differently by the accountant of another budget organization.

Keywords: accounting transaction, card, expense estimate, general monthly, preferential monthly card, transportation cards, economic transaction.

INTRODUCTION

Along with the reforms implemented in all sectors and systems of the country during the years of independence, profound structural changes and modernization were also observed in the State Budget system.

In particular, to further reform the budget system for the implementation of the state budget treasury, to strengthen control over the intended use of budget funds using modern information technologies, increasing the effectiveness of budget revenue and expenditure management at all levels was gradually achieved.¹

ANALYSIS

¹ Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

During 2000-2010, the legislative framework for the budget system and the implementation of the state budget was adopted, and the composition of the budget system budgets and state budget structures was determined.

A new procedure for the preparation, approval, implementation and control of budgets has been introduced. Since 2010, budgets of all levels of the budget system have been consolidated into a single budget execution account, which has created the opportunity to form current and consolidated information on budget execution.

In turn, the introduction of budget execution led to the need to implement reforms in the budget accounting and reporting system.

In this regard, in 2010-2017, legislative documents related to budget accounting and reporting were adopted.

First, the manual "On Accounting in Budget Organizations" on the organization and maintenance of accounting in budgetary organizations financed from the state budget was put into practice.

Rules have been developed for the preparation, approval and submission of periodic financial reports of organizations funded from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The procedure for budget execution accounting "On the accounting of budget execution of the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and state target funds" was put into practice. These procedures and rules for budget accounting and reporting served to form systematic information on the budget execution of the budget system.

The Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in 2013 in order to unify into a single system the regulatory legal documents that were in force during the transition period on the preparation, review, approval, registration, implementation of the budget, relations and settlements between budgets, and control over budget execution.

The Budget Code established the legal basis not only for the budget system, but also for relations and processes related to budget accounting, reporting, and control.²

The development of digital technologies, the increasing integration of the economies of the countries of the world, the large-scale involvement of the financial resources of international financial organizations in the country's economy in the context of the financial and economic crisis increasing the effectiveness of the implementation of the budget system of the states on an international scale by strengthening competition, ensuring the openness and transparency of information on the implementation of the budget and, in turn, improving the flexibility of the budget execution accounting and reporting system.

For this reason, the Budget Code and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2022” and the “Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Support for Innovative Ideas and Technologies” were adopted In order to ensure the implementation of the state program, to further improve budget accounting by harmonizing financial reporting in the public sector with international standards, and to ensure the transparency of budget reporting, standards for budget accounting are being gradually adopted.³

International practice shows that financial statements prepared in accordance with international standards are distinguished by their high information potential and relevance to the user.

In this context, it is appropriate to familiarize ourselves with foreign experiences in improving accounting in the public sector based on international accounting standards.

In the 1970s, Switzerland, one of the European countries, adopted the "traditional" method of organizing accounting in the public sector management

² On amendments and additions to the Instruction on accounting in budget organizations. Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 20, 2025, registration number 2169-9

³ Republic of Uzbekistan “Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2022” and the “Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Support for Innovative Ideas and Technologies” were adopted

system, namely cash accounting (accounting is based on the receipts and expenditures of cash). After the 1970s, reforms began to be implemented in public sector accounting, and the transition to the accrual method began.

In the public sector, all standards were developed in 2004 based on international accounting standards and have been fully implemented since 2007.

As a result of the introduction of these standards, some changes have been made to ensure that accounting is conducted in a new accounting method.

In Great Britain, a decision was made in 1995 to implement budgeting and financial reporting on the basis of IPSAS standards. This process was carried out in stages, and it was determined that consolidated financial statements would be prepared from March 31, 2007 (the end of the financial year). In France, reforms in the budget accounting system began in 2001, and in 2004 a working group of accounting experts from the Ministry of Finance was created to develop new standards, and accounting standards similar to IPSAS were developed and are currently in force. In China, the reform of public sector accounting is being carried out based on the experience of Western countries.

They are mainly based on the models of Great Britain and the United States. In our country, based on international practical experience, special attention is currently being paid to reforming budget accounting.⁴

CONCLUSION

1. Complete adaptation of the calculation of the execution of budgets of the budget system to the method of calculation in accordance with the requirements of international accounting standards;

2. Formation of a single accounting balance on the account of the execution of the budgets of the budget system (state budget, state purpose funds, extra-budgetary funds of budget organizations);

⁴ Republic of Uzbekistan “Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2022” and the “Year of Active Entrepreneurship, Support for Innovative Ideas and Technologies” were adopted

3. Bringing financial reports on the implementation of budgets of the budget system into a single system, that is, ensuring that financial reports are available in a uniform form in budgets of all levels;

4. Step-by-step implementation of the practice of obtaining a qualification certificate for specialists responsible for budget accounting and reporting, as well as systematically promoting qualification improvement;

5. To improve the information systems for budget accounting and reporting in order to adapt them to the requirements of the adopted Budget Accounting Standards.

In conclusion, it is positive that the above-mentioned points be taken into account in future reforms of budget accounting and reporting.

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1. Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2. On amendments and additions to the Instruction on accounting in budget organizations. Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 20, 2025, registration number 2169-9

3. On amendments to the Instruction on accounting in budget organizations. Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 30, 2024, registration number 2169-8

4. On approval of the Instruction on accounting in budget organizations. Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 22, 2010, registration number 2169.